

Supporting Information

Optimizing Effective Potentials via Gradient-Enhanced Surrogates for Quantum Embedding

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S1. Proof of equation (36) in the main manuscript

For a closed-shell restricted KS calculation,

$$D_{mn}^{X,(i)} = 2 \sum_{p \in \text{occ}_X} C_{mp}^{X,(i)} C_{np}^{X,(i)} \quad (1)$$

where $C_{mp}^{X,(i)}$ is the coefficient of occupied molecular orbital (MO) p projected on AO m for the subsystem X .

Now, perturb one auxiliary coefficient, $v_l \rightarrow v_l + \delta v_l$. Because $V_{\text{emb}}(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_k v_k f_k(\mathbf{r})$, the 1st-order perturbation to the one-electron KS Hamiltonian from changing v_l is $\delta \hat{h} = f_l(\mathbf{r}) \delta v_l$. In the MO basis of subsystem X , this perturbation has the matrix element

$$\delta \hat{h}_{qp}^{X,(i)} = \langle \psi_q^{X,(i)} | f_l(\mathbf{r}) | \psi_p^{X,(i)} \rangle \delta v_l \quad (2)$$

For a nondegenerate occupied MO p , the 1st-order perturbation theory gives

$$\delta \psi_p^{X,(i)} = \sum_{q \neq p} \psi_q^{X,(i)} \frac{\langle \psi_q^{X,(i)} | f_l(\mathbf{r}) | \psi_p^{X,(i)} \rangle}{\varepsilon_p^{X,(i)} - \varepsilon_q^{X,(i)}} \delta v_l \quad (3)$$

Only occupied-virtual rotations change the closed-shell density, so we keep only $q \in \text{vir}_X$:

$$\frac{\partial C_{mp}^X}{\partial v_l} = \sum_{q \in \text{vir}_X} C_{mq}^{X,(i)} \frac{\langle \psi_q^{X,(i)} | f_l(\mathbf{r}) | \psi_p^{X,(i)} \rangle}{\varepsilon_p^{X,(i)} - \varepsilon_q^{X,(i)}} \quad (4)$$

Then differentiate the density matrix (eq. (1)):

$$\left. \frac{\partial D_{mn}^X}{\partial v_l} \right|_{\mathbf{v}=\mathbf{v}_i} = 2 \sum_{p \in \text{occ}_X} \left[\frac{\partial C_{mp}^{X,(i)}}{\partial v_l} C_{np}^{X,(i)} + C_{mp}^{X,(i)} \frac{\partial C_{np}^{X,(i)}}{\partial v_l} \right] \quad (5)$$

Substituting the orbital response expression gives,

$$\left. \frac{\partial D_{mn}^X}{\partial v_l} \right|_{\mathbf{v}=\mathbf{v}_i} = 2 \sum_{p \in \text{occ}_X} \sum_{q \in \text{vir}_X} \frac{C_{mq}^{X,(i)} C_{np}^{X,(i)} + C_{mp}^{X,(i)} C_{nq}^{X,(i)}}{\varepsilon_p^{X,(i)} - \varepsilon_q^{X,(i)}} \langle \psi_p^{X,(i)} | f_l(\mathbf{r}) | \psi_q^{X,(i)} \rangle \quad (6)$$

S2. Proof of equation (39) in the main manuscript

For a closed-shell restricted KS calculation,

$$D_{mn}^{X,(i)} = 2 \sum_{p \in \text{occ}_X} C_{mp}^{X,(i)} C_{np}^{X,(i)} \quad (1)$$

where $C_{mp}^{X,(i)}$ is the coefficient of occupied molecular orbital (MO) p projected on AO m for the subsystem X .

The density matrix response is

$$\left. \frac{\partial D_{mn}^X}{\partial v_l} \right|_{\mathbf{v}=\mathbf{v}_i} = 2 \sum_{p \in \text{occ}_X} \sum_{q \in \text{vir}_X} \frac{C_{mq}^{X,(i)} C_{np}^{X,(i)} + C_{mp}^{X,(i)} C_{nq}^{X,(i)}}{\varepsilon_p^{X,(i)} - \varepsilon_q^{X,(i)}} \langle \psi_p^{X,(i)} | f_l(\mathbf{r}) | \psi_q^{X,(i)} \rangle \quad (2)$$

with

$$\langle \psi_p^{X,(i)} | f_l(\mathbf{r}) | \psi_q^{X,(i)} \rangle = \sum_{m,n}^{N_{\text{AO}}} C_{mp}^{X,(i)} B_{mn,l} C_{nq}^{X,(i)} \quad (3)$$

where $\psi_p^{X,(i)}$ is the p -th occupied MO in the i -th iteration for the subsystem X , and q is the index of the unoccupied MOs in the virtual space. The gap between the occupied and unoccupied MO orbital energies is $\varepsilon_p^{X,(i)} - \varepsilon_q^{X,(i)}$. We contract this response with

$$B_{mn,k} = \int \phi_m(\mathbf{r}) f_k(\mathbf{r}) \phi_n(\mathbf{r}) d\mathbf{r} \quad (4)$$

where m and n label AOs, and f_k is auxiliary function.

For real-valued orbitals and real-valued auxiliary functions, and notice that p and q are dummy indices,

$$\sum_{m,n} C_{mq} C_{np} = \sum_{m,n} C_{mp} C_{nq} \text{ and } B_{mn,k} = B_{nm,k} \quad (5)$$

By exchanging the dummy indices m with n , we have

$$\sum_{m,n} B_{mn,k} C_{mq} C_{np} = \sum_{mn} B_{nm,k} C_{nq} C_{mp} = \sum_{mn} B_{mn,k} C_{mp} C_{nq} \quad (6)$$

Therefore,

$$\sum_{m,n} B_{mn,k} (C_{mq} C_{np} + C_{mp} C_{nq}) = 2 \langle \psi_p^{X,(i)} | f_k(\mathbf{r}) | \psi_q^{X,(i)} \rangle \quad (7)$$

Since the linear-response (LR) Hessian of the Wu-Yang functional is

$$H_{i,kl}^{\text{LR}} = \sum_{X=\text{cls,env}} \sum_{m,n} B_{mn,k} \left(\left. \frac{\partial D_{mn}^X}{\partial v_l} \right|_{\mathbf{v}=\mathbf{v}_i} \right) + 2\lambda L_{kl} \quad (8)$$

then,

$$H_{i,kl}^{\text{LR}} = 4 \sum_{X=\text{cls,env}} \sum_{p \in \text{occ}_X} \sum_{q \in \text{vir}_X} \frac{\langle \psi_p^{X,(i)} | f_k(\mathbf{r}) | \psi_q^{X,(i)} \rangle \langle \psi_q^{X,(i)} | f_l(\mathbf{r}) | \psi_p^{X,(i)} \rangle}{\varepsilon_p^{X,(i)} - \varepsilon_q^{X,(i)}} + 2\lambda L_{kl} \quad (9)$$

S3. Detailed energetics along the reaction coordinates for benchmark.

Table S1. Relative energies (in eV) along the reaction coordinate (\AA) for C_2H_4 dimerization on Li metal.

Reaction coordinate (\AA)	PBE0 (all-atom)	ECW (with surrogate V_{emb})	ECW (with T-E V_{emb})	NEVPT2 (all-atom)
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
3.08	0.29	0.23	0.23	0.28
6.17	0.47	0.43	0.44	0.44
9.27	0.52	0.47	0.48	0.49
11.38	0.45	0.87	0.87	0.90
13.48	-0.81	-0.29	-0.29	-0.28
15.57	-0.85	-0.36	-0.36	-0.34

Table S2. Relative energies (in eV) along the reaction coordinate (\AA) for $\text{N}(\text{ads}) + \text{H}(\text{ads}) \rightarrow \text{NH}(\text{ads})$ on Mo-doped Cu.

Reaction coordinate (\AA)	PBE0 (all-atom)	ECW (with surrogate V_{emb})	QM/QM (no V_{emb})	NEVPT2 (all-atom)
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.80	0.13	-0.02	-0.58	-0.03
1.60	0.84	0.43	-0.44	0.31
2.29	0.32	0.50	-0.05	0.53
2.99	-0.25	-0.24	-0.41	-0.22

Table S3. Relative energies (in eV) along the F–H separation (\AA) for the proton transfer between F^- and $\text{F}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4$.

F–H separation (\AA)	PBE0 (all-atom)	ECW (with surrogate V_{emb})	ECW (with T-E V_{emb})	NEVPT2 (all-atom)
1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
1.10	0.39	0.40	0.40	0.36
1.20	0.91	0.94	0.95	0.89
1.30	1.45	1.51	1.52	1.45
1.40	1.95	2.03	2.04	1.99
1.50	2.38	2.47	2.48	2.47
1.60	2.73	2.83	2.84	2.86
1.70	2.97	3.10	3.11	3.15
1.80	3.13	3.26	3.27	3.30
1.90	3.18	3.30	3.30	3.31
2.00	3.15	3.22	3.23	3.19
2.10	3.03	3.06	3.06	3.02
2.20	2.85	2.84	2.84	2.82
2.30	2.66	2.62	2.61	2.60
2.40	2.55	2.50	2.50	2.48
2.50	2.73	2.69	2.69	2.67

Table S4. Relative energies (in eV) along the reaction coordinate (\AA) for the N- NO_2 bond scission in RDX trimer.

Reaction coordinate (\AA)	PBE0 (all-atom)	ECW (with surrogate V_{emb})	NEVPT2 (all-atom)
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
1.35	-0.07	-0.02	-0.02
2.69	-2.53	-0.99	-1.02
4.17	-3.19	-1.54	-1.57

S4. Optimized active spaces.

Figure S1. The optimized active space (8e, 8o) for the starting structure of adsorbed C_2H_4 on Li metal. This active space, optimized for the whole system, was used for all-atom NEVPT2. Atom color code: brown – C, white – H, green – Li.

Figure S2. The optimized active space (6e, 6o) for the starting structure of adsorbed C_2H_4 on Li metal. This active space, optimized for the carved cluster (Li_2 in green) under the embedding potential, was used for ECW energies. Atom color code: brown – C, white – H, green – Li in the carved cluster, navy blue – Li in the environment.

Figure S3. The optimized active space (10e, 10o) for the adsorbed N and adsorbed H on Mo-doped Cu. This active space, optimized for the carved cluster (Mo_2 in pink, and Cu_4 in blue) under the embedding potential, was used for ECW energies. Atom color code: pink – Mo, blue – Cu in the carved cluster, white – H, cerulean – N, grey – Cu in the environment.

Figure S4. The optimized active space (10e, 10o) for the adsorbed NH on Mo-doped Cu. This active space, optimized for the carved cluster (Mo₂ in pink, and Cu₄ in blue) under the embedding potential, was used for ECW energies. Atom color code: pink – Mo, blue – Cu in the carved cluster, white – H, cerulean – N, grey – Cu in the environment.

Figure S5. The optimized active space (4e, 4o) for the F⁻...H⁺...F(H₂O)₄ system. This active space, optimized for the carved cluster (F⁻...H⁺...F) under the embedding potential, was used for ECW energies. Atom color code: white – H, periwinkle – F, blue – (H₂O)₄ in the environment.

Figure S6. The optimized active space (2e, 2o) for the N-NO₂ bond scission in the RDX trimer system. This active space, optimized for the carved cluster (the RDX unit in the center) under the embedding potential, was used for ECW energies. Atom color code: red – O, blue – N, grey – C, white – H, dark grey – atoms in the environment (the two RDX units on the sides).